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Sensibility and Control in Hannah More's *Sensibility* and *The Cheap Repository Tracts*

Dr. Madhvi Zutshi
Dept. of English,
SGTB Khalsa College,
University of Delhi.

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Abstract:

This study examines how the eighteenth-century writer Hannah More negotiates the tension between the idea of sensibility and reason in her poem “Sensibility: An Epistle to the Honourable Mrs. Boscawen” (1785) and her moral tales for the working class published in a series titled *The Cheap Repository Tracts* (1795-98). These Tracts - a series of essays, stories and poems - were conceived by Hannah More to counter the revolutionary effects of Thomas Paine’s *Rights of Man* and to which she contributed over fifty titles. In her poem *Sensibility*, feelings or passions are domiciled primarily in the domestic space, but sensibility is valorised in the poem as it is extended beyond the family into public service. On the other hand, her stories in the tracts for the working class explore an opposition between sensibility and reason but eventually fail to harness the radical potential in the idea of sensibility. These political tracts, disguised as simple tales for the less educated, offer an example of how the upper classes in the eighteenth century sought to control popular culture through a moralistic caution for the poor not to question their place.

Keywords: Hannah More, *Sensibility*, late eighteenth-century popular culture, *Cheap Repository Tracts*.

Introduction

Hannah More (1745-1833) was a prolific British writer from the late eighteenth century who has largely been ignored in much scholarship because of her conservative views. Her tales in *The Cheap Repository Tracts* have often been read as attempts to encourage the working poor to embrace poverty as a virtue and to preach to them hard work as their sacred duty in order to earn compassion from the rich (Scheuermann 2002). This article suggests a more complex view of More's tales. Hannah More has also been read as heralding some of the regressive values towards the working class in the Victorian age (Stott 2003). It is important to see how the antiradical tradition that More was a part of, impacted culture in Britain in the late eighteenth century (Gilmartin 2003). Hannah More's evangelical style was subtle in its aim to influence and control the working class and offers us a sense of how the upper classes were trying to control popular culture (Pedersen 1986). This article examines the tension between impulse/feeling/passions -- terms she often uses as synonyms for sensibility in her poem *Sensibility* -- and reason by examining a similar tension marked by her between sensibility and reason in the moral tales she wrote for the *Cheap Repository Tracts* series. This article suggests that there is an ambivalence where More cannot evade the feeling of compassion for the plight of the poor but limits it as a privilege for upper classes without fulfilling the radical potential that was possible in these compassionate feelings.

Sensibility: A Retraction from Benevolence

Hannah More's poem *Sensibility: An Epistle to the Honourable Mrs. Boscawen* (subsequently abbreviated to *Sensibility* in this article), gathers together both the indefinable and contentious nature of the phenomenon of eighteenth-century idea of sensibility and evokes a series of

contradictory ideas about it. The idea of sensibility in More's poem, partakes of a natural morality yet is not inherently virtuous. Sensibility is tied to benevolence and virtue, but in its meaning, the term hovers between material charity towards the poor and spiritual ministering towards those suffering. Sensibility is described most often in the poem with the epithet 'melting', and this inexpressible emotion cannot be marked or recorded because supposed physical manifestations like gestures and sighs may be fake. Moreover, art cannot capture it though sensibility may enhance the power of art.

The background to the poem *Sensibility* (1785) was the deaths of two people -- one known to Hannah More, the actor David Garrick, and the other, the son of her friend Mrs. Frances Boscawen, who is alluded to in the title. The poem is addressed to Frances Boscawen and refers to Mrs. Boscawen's complex grief at having lost a son in battle. The poem elevates the mother's grief by emphasizing the ennobling quality of emotional pain. The poem's speaker points out the mixed nature of all intense pleasures like those associated with parenthood, which are inevitably tinged with pain – a complex passion of pain mixed with pleasure -- either of calamities that have fallen on one's children or the anxious dread of such calamities. The poem then moves on to eulogize sensibility – which is capitalized and personified - for its virtues. The poem ends with a rhetorical question to Mrs. Boscawen about her other son who is also in battle and for whom she dreads a similar fate as the deceased one. The poem's speaker points out the virtuous mother's feelings who intuit a similar passionate nature in her son which may impel him to risk his life in a battle and the mother's desire for and appreciation of such a quality which is passionate and selfless, and yet which may make her a bereaved mother once again.

The poem repeatedly celebrates the energy and heightened quality of intense emotion, usually associating it with pain. The poem's speaker views avoidance of attachments or acute feelings to

preserve oneself from suffering as a self-interested and cold, complacent happiness, which the speaker names "a sordid joy". Even the pleasures of love are tinged with an inevitable sense of peril, as "sorrows grafted on enjoyments grow". Suffering as a superior mode of being to a state of indifference, is the consolation the speaker offers the addressee, a bereaved mother, asking her "Yet would you change that sense acute to gain/ A dear-bought absence from the poignant pain:/Commuting every grief those feelings give, /In loveless, joyless apathy to live" (lines 117-120). The speaker exalts pain by associating it with a refined sensibility, a "fine-wrought spirit", a physical capacity which permeates and animates the body: "where glow exalted sense and taste refin'd, / There keener anguish rankles in the mind;/ There, feeling is diffus'd through every part, / Thrills in each nerve, and lives in all the heart" (69-72). All comfort is dismissed as futile in such a state of grief -- "Can all the boasted powers of wit and song, / Of life one pang remove, one hour prolong?" (75-6).

The particular bereavement of the addressee here, i.e. a personal grief tinged with the pride of having given up a son for the nation, allows the speaker to make the shift in describing anguish as moving beyond a merely personal sorrow to the finer feelings of self-sacrifice and social sympathy. The speaker defines the "vulgar" undesirable readers of her poem as those "who ne'er the high heroic duty know, / For public good the private to forego" (142-2). The virtuous know "the rule of holy sympathy to keep, / Joy for the joyful, tears for them that weep" (147-8). Ambivalence over the nature of sensibility as personal or social is evident in the nature of the space it is to reside in. The poem shifts between placing sensibility within the confines of the family, which would allow it to be private, and seeks to show that because it extends beyond the self to the family, it is also a social feeling. The "almost sacred joys of Home depend" on sensibility, in which place it should

rightfully reign. The domestic space, though seen as private, is also a social space that makes a person move beyond himself:

A solitary bliss thou ne'er could'st find,
Thy joys with those thou lov'st are interwin'd
And he, whose helpful tenderness removes
The rankling thorn which wounds the breast he loves. (321-24)

The poem then moves on to expand the realm of sensibility from the domestic space to a larger society, where an impulsive goodness to strangers is possible. In the poem, the large-heartedness of the virtuous is clearly marked by a benevolence that, befitting the state of sensibility, will always be spontaneous as well as unsuspecting of the credibility of the sufferer. Pity is to be showered unprompted on the sufferer -- "and mercy stretching out ere want can speak" (163). Charity and thoughtful caution cannot go together, the latter being perceived as often stalling the flow of goodwill - "Benevolence, which seldom stays to choose, / Lest pausing prudence tempt her to refuse" (155-56). Further in the poem, the speaker warns the reader that any forethought or caution on the part of the benevolent may become a cover for an undetected meanness of heart, an excuse to withhold generosity. Only an impulsive perception of a situation requiring relief can be evidence of true benevolence:

And while Discretion all our views should guide,
Beware, lest secret aims and ends she hides...
Beware, lest Prudence self become unjust...

Prudence must never be suspicion's slave,

The world's wise man is more than half a knave. (191-98)

It is also clear that for the speaker, the inchoate and amorphous nature of sensibility is seen as liberating. The poem addresses "Sweet SENSIBILITY" as that whose "subtle essence still eludes the chains of definition" (235-36). In a series of epithets addressing the power of sensibility, what emerges are the intrinsic links of sensibility with both morality and an unguarded impetuosity:

“Sweet SENSIBILITY! Thou keen delight

Unprompted moral! Sullen sense of light!

Perception exquisite! Fair virtue's seed!

Thou quick precursor of the lib'ral deed!

Thou hasty conscience! Reason's blushing morn!

Instinctive kindness e'er reflection's born!

Prompt sense of equity! To thee belongs

The swift redress of unexamin'd wrongs (237-44)

The use of quick-paced tributes to the varied powers of sensibility embodies its impulsive thrust, its unguarded quality, and its lack of circumspection. Sensibility is seen as a quality that somehow manages to guide the benefactor to naturally attach himself or herself to the social underdog and is "always apt to choose the suff'ring side" (246).

However, the inexpressible nature of sensibility elicits an anxiety about how to judge those who may be possessed of it. A familiar butt of ridicule in the poem are those people who shed tears over

non-human subjects, for example over dead animals for whom sorrow is disproportionately expressed according to the speaker, or for fictional characters whose miseries are after all, well, only 'fictional'. Such sympathy is viewed as wasted because "real mis'ry unrelieved retires!" (254). The speaker determines sensibility by the objects that it chooses. Nevertheless, the anxiety to preserve sensibility as ennobling, creates an 'other' in the poem, a 'false' sensibility that is draped in sighs, tears, words, and art, and which may prove to be deceptive and could be a hypocritical mask for the devious. The speaker is ambivalent about sensibility depicted in art. Art is seen as channelling away charitable feelings of readers/viewers from the real needs of real people. However, for the poem's speaker, Thomas Gray's poem *Elegy* is enhanced in its charms because sensibility "makes the pensive strains of Gray / Win to the open heart their easy way" (367-68).

In the celebration of sensibility in the penultimate part of the poem, sensibility's exaltation is founded on the idea of an active redressal of wrongs. It is described as the "LOVE DIVINE! Sole source of charity" (283). The poem points to those in situations of poverty such as "starving children" but towards the end of the poem, there is a hasty qualification as to the kinds of benevolence possible. The speaker is quick to add that "not that by deeds alone this love's express'd / If so, the affluent only were the bless'd". The poem tries to balance two kinds of meanings of sensibility that are identified here strongly with benevolence. One kind of meaning links benevolent sensibility as an unselfish extension of material help to the oppressed poor. The other instinct in the poem is to pull the definition of benevolence away from material charity, so that those in a state of deprivation can also partake of this feeling. It is implied that people of all classes could have a kind word or prayer to offer others. So, sensibility becomes a quality that can grant spiritual equality to all.

The radical aspect of sensibility can potentially be possessed by everyone and this is apparent in Hannah More's famous abolitionist poem, *Slavery*. In this poem, not only is sentiment typically deployed to engage the sympathies of a British audience to abolish the slave trade by showing, for instance, how families of enslaved people are torn apart when sold into slavery. More importantly, sensibility in this poem is projected as the basis for equality between whites and the enslaved, as the poem points to the erroneous notion of whites that Africans do not have feelings to the same extent as others -- "Plead not, in reason's palpable abuse, / Their sense of feeling callous and obtuse". It is the capacity for strong feelings which humanises the enslaved and demands their liberty as humans, even as the poem undermines this feeling by stating that reason may be lacking in the enslaved -- "Tho' few can reason, all mankind can feel" (line 150).

However, in More's poem *Sensibility*, a change in social inequalities is deemed impossible. Instead, the poem emphasizes the enormous good possible in the accruing of smaller deeds of kindness and in sensitivity towards others' feelings. The poem shifts from defining benevolence in less material and more spiritual terms. Restraint of anger and "the large aggregate of little things" (316) is presented as an equally good alternative to social change.

Towards the end of the poem, there is a retraction of the link between sensibility and benevolent feelings in a somewhat illogical move. The speaker notes that those who have sensibility would be affected rather more deeply by the harsh words of others. The speaker then shifts the focus from those who are affected by the harsh words or deeds, to those who inflict them and suggests that strong feeling could intensify the deployment of harshness. Feeling becomes a force that energizes existent dispositions, whether they are good or evil. The poem neutralizes the morality of feeling by delinking it from benevolence -- "as FEELING tends to good or leans to ill, / It gives fresh force to vice or principle;/ Tis not a gift peculiar to the good" (339-41).

Even the physical thrust of feeling is viewed in the poem as dubious. The imagery of sensibility's physiological component changes to a negative one. The earlier suggestion of the "finely-fashioned nerve" in the poem which was exalted as an instance of refined sensibility is transformed into an image of blood circulation which needs to be channelled into its proper course. Wisdom, reason, and religion are crowned as the caretakers of virtue and are shown as needed in order to restrain "wild irregular desires, /disorder'd passions, and illicit fires" (349-50). The impetuosity of virtue, earlier celebrated, is by at the end of the poem eyed with suspicion as possibly disturbing the orderliness of social and religious laws. Though the end of the poem notes the charms of sensibility's power to induce valour and sacrifice, the see-sawing between passion and reason in its penultimate lines breaks the unqualified triumph of the former over the latter.

The Cheap Repository Tracts: Controlling popular culture

"The message to be given to the labouring poor was simple, and was summarized by Burke in the famine year of 1795: 'Patience, labour, sobriety, frugality and religion, should be recommended to them; all the rest is downright fraud'. The sensibility of the Victorian middle class was nurtured in the 1790s by frightened gentry who had seen miners, potters and cutlers reading *Rights of Man*, and its foster-parents were William Wilberforce and Hannah More. It was in these counter-revolutionary decades that the humanitarian tradition became warped beyond recognition" (Thompson 60-61). This section of the article examines the particular manner in which Hannah More's *Cheap Repository Tracts* both invokes and problematizes the humanitarian aspects of sensibility, in ways more complex than in E.P. Thompson's account of her in the quoted passage.

The confusion noted in Hannah More's poem over sensibility and its link to benevolence is glimpsed in some of the narratives in More's *The Cheap Repository Tracts*, which test the limits

of the link between both qualities. Her moral tales were published as part of the *Cheap Repository Tracts* by the religious Clapham sect in order to provide appropriate reading material to the labouring classes, and to counter the ill-effects of revolutionary ideas, popularized by Thomas Paine's *Rights of Man*. More's stories aim to teach reasoning abilities to those experiencing poverty in order to enable the privileged classes to deploy morality and religion as a means of quieting discontent about inequality and oppression. In some of the stories, the kind of 'virtuous poor' who are represented are shown as industrious workers, who refuse to drink gin and who show gratitude towards God even for the meagre resources they have. Their virtue is also shown in their refusal to cheat their privileged clients, for example, in the story of the Hackney Coachman, who charges the correct fare from gentlemen, and in the story of Betty, the St. Giles Orange Girl, who learns that she must not slip in a rotten orange to an unsuspecting customer. Tale after tale makes it clear that according to More, the poor have abundant means, if only they could be taught economizing skills.

The narrator through the tales, attempts to simplify difficult economic statistics for the untutored, and presumes to paraphrase complex philosophical debates for the benefit of the uninitiated. In the tale titled *Village Politics*, Jack uses the statistical example of two and a half million pounds being given in poor rates to defeat the arguments of the character Tom who is influenced by Thomas Paine. In *Betty Brown*, *The St. Giles Orange Girl*, a lady – the wife of a justice of peace – explains to Betty the complex and unjust method of interest being extracted from her by Mrs. Sponge, a loan shark. In the short ballad titled *Dan and Jane*, the philosophical debate over faith vs. good works is simplified. Two gardeners – a couple – after arguing over which idea is worthier, come to 'realise' that the concepts are inseparable; that faith equals the root of a tree, and good works are akin to the fruit.

In two of the tales *Village Politics* and *The Riot*, that explicitly challenge revolutionary ideas (here primarily associated with Paine), the narrator posits the rebellious character Tom as a passionate figure who could lead unreasonable and illicit actions like riots. The other figure, Jack, embodies reason and he espouses a status-quo position as the safest. Jack represents workers as persons who are patient with difficult economic conditions and resistant to radical social change. In the tales' discourse, reason is the quality to be encouraged in these volatile times but it must be the kind of reason which views violent action against socio-economic inequality as undue discontentment. The friction between reason and passion breaks down at moments when reason cannot answer the questions of equality that the passionate worker demands. Jack realizes that his reasoning may fail to convince Tom, as the reasons for revolt seem compelling. At such moments, Jack falters, and abandoning the calm method of deductive reasoning, he alternates between cajoling and using threats to stop a rebellion.

Another tale published in the tracts, *The History of Mr. Fantom, The New-Fashioned Philosopher and His Man William*, is an example of the ambiguous status Hannah More grants to benevolent feelings born of impulse. The story details the moral downfall of William, the footman of Mr. Fantom, a retired gentleman trader and a new-fangled philosopher. Mr. Fantom is a wealthy trader, who in a fit of vanity to distinguish himself, decides to take on the mantle of a philosopher and retires into the country as an 'idle' thinker. He reads Paine and absorbs his 'wicked' ideas on atheism and reform. Fantom's views on social change are depicted as too ambitious to be accomplishable and therefore appear to be an excuse to avoid the active intervention he could make for the benefit of his servants or fellow parishioners. His vision of a world without war and prisons is clearly ridiculed in the tale as at best, far-fetched and at worst, dangerous. Fantom's guest in his country house, Mr. Trueman, is meant as a foil to Fantom and functions as the moral centre

of the tale. Trueman is a trader, figured as a hard-working, god-fearing and charitable man. As the story progresses, Fantom's lack of concern for those around him, like his family or servants or anyone in need of charity, is repeatedly made the butt of humour. For instance, after avowing his indifference to a vulgar object like money, Fantom wriggles out of a donation request made by Trueman for an imprisoned man's family. However, his utter hypocrisy as a socially-committed philosopher is exposed in the tale when he refuses to show concern as his gardener's cottage catches fire. In fact, he rebukes his daughter for interrupting his social tête-à-tête for such a 'minor distraction'. Trueman, on the other hand, jumps up and runs to help, forgetting his hat in his concern. Trueman leaps into the fire, ignoring danger to his person in order to save a baby trapped inside the burning cottage. After the incident, when Fantom still refuses to help his crisis-ridden employee, Trueman arranges for a relief fund from fellow-tradesmen for the gardener, gets his wife to sew clothes for the poverty-stricken family and helps to rehabilitate them. In all this, it is clear that the contrast between the two men is that Fantom shows mere lip-service to benevolence, and Trueman reveals an impulsive attitude to those in need.

But what is striking about Trueman's portrayal is that after he illustrates the need to provide real help to those in need, he articulates a rejection of benevolence through material intervention, seeing this as a crass definition, and sees spiritual comfort as the best form of benevolence. In his gifts of charity to the family, he adds a parcel of books "which always made a part of his charities; as he used to say, there was something cruel in that kindness which was anxious to relieve the bodies of men, but was negligent of their souls" (15).

The second half of the tale satirizes Fantom's philosophizing more centrally - not only does it render him insensitive to his environs and the people around him, but his philosophy also becomes farcical as he attempts to bridge the intellectual gap between himself and his servants. His trusted

footman William has heard snatches of his master's conversation about "private vices and publick benefits" and William decides to take this most seriously by indulging in vices like idleness and drink. William is dismissed from service and subsequently steals some silver spoons from Fantom. William is then caught, jailed, and presumably hanged. Again, Fantom shows little remorse for being partly responsible for William's downfall. We are reminded that Fantom had always forbidden his servants to go to church on Sundays, and instead had persuaded them to read Thomas Paine. Trueman once again displays sympathy for Fantom's servant and expresses concern about William's salvation, while Fantom only worries over his lost silver spoons. The story makes it clear that philosophy, at least of some kinds, can harden the hearts of the privileged and can spell disaster for the poor.

Conclusion

While in the two ballads discussed, reason had been accorded a quality of morality, in the tale of Fantom and Trueman there is a suspicion of reason as a tool that is often used to rationalize a lack of social commitment, a suspicion that also marked the middle parts of More's poem *Sensibility*. Fantom, the politically radical philosopher, is shown as incapable of engineering social changes that uplift the poor. Instead, he proves to be dangerous by upsetting the existent social order without any concrete gains for the poor and inciting them towards discontentment and crime. The character of Trueman however, recalls the ambivalence with which Hannah More had defined sensibility and benevolence in her poem. Trueman has an impulsive generosity and he reaches out to relieve those suffering before his eyes. But the connection of suffering as very often linked to crises arising from states of poverty is made invisible. The radical potential of sensibility that can induce benevolence is not fully realized. Though Hannah More grapples with the virtue of sympathy and

benevolence that is potentially a part of sensibility in her poem, she tempers it with various qualifications. The tales show a similar ambiguity. Hannah More's writing is a testimony to the conservative deployment of what was considered a benevolent virtue like sensibility. Her continuation of the use of feelings to influence and control the working classes in service of the privileged class, speaks to the sustained efforts by the upper classes in seeking to contain the revolutionary ideas both in the idea of sensibility and in the working class.

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